

Effect of parasitism on the productivity of the ommastrephid stocks in Galician waters (NW Spain): economic loss

Efecto del parasitismo en la productividad de los stocks de omastrefidos en aguas de Galicia: pérdidas económicas

Santiago PASCUAL*, Ángel F. GONZÁLEZ** and Ángel GUERRA**

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ABSTRACT

The economic loss due to the effect of parasitism of the ommastrephid stocks are estimated using the interannual values of prevalence of infestation by *Pennella* sp. in the ommastrephid stocks of *Illex coindetii* and *Todaropsis eblanae* in the Galician coast. Parasitism of *Pennella* sp. implies about 2.1% and 8.1% of the variation in condition of the ommastrephids, reducing the condition of *I. coindetii* and *T. eblanae* over 8.8% and 21.1%, respectively. It was estimated that the reduction in biomass of infested squid were 143 and 527 tonnes for *I. coindetii* and *T. eblanae*, respectively for the period 1980-1991. Assuming an average value of 125 ptas/kg of squid, the annual economic loss for the fishery sector due to the infested stock is thus estimated in some 84 millions ptas for the period 1980-1991. This overview highlights that parasitism is not only an important zoonotic problem but an important economic problem at the time of management of infested stocks.

RESUMEN

En este trabajo se estiman las pérdidas económicas debidas al parasitismo de *Pennella* sp. en los stocks de omastrefidos de las costas gallegas. El parasitismo de *Pennella* sp. en *Illex coindetii* y *Todaropsis eblanae* implica un variación de la condición de los animales de un 2,1% y un 8,1%, lo que supone un decrecimiento de un 8,8% y un 21,1% en la condición de estas especies. Se estimó que la reducción en biomasa fue de 143 y 527 toneladas para *I. coindetii* y *T. eblanae*, respectivamente, durante el período 1980-1991. Asumiendo un precio medio de 125 ptas/kg de pota, la pérdida del sector fue de aproximadamente 84 millones de ptas durante el periodo 1980-1991. Este estudio resalta que el parasitismo no es sólo un problema zoonótico importante sino también un importante problema económico a la hora del manejo de stocks infestados.

KEY WORDS: *Illex coindetii*, *Todaropsis eblanae*, parasitism, *Pennella* sp., stock productivity.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Illex coindetii*, *Todaropsis eblanae*, parasitismo, *Pennella* sp., productividad del stock.

INTRODUCTION

Cephalopods are growth-rapid molluscs and their growth rates are affected by biotic and abiotic factors (FORSYTHE AND VAN HEUKELEM, 1987;

FORSYTHE, 1993). These marine molluscs constitutes an important resource within the marine ecosystems and their importance increase every year (CADDY, 1989;

* Laboratorio de Parasitología. Facultad de Ciencias del Mar, Universidad de Vigo, Apdo. 874, Vigo, Spain.

** Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas (CSIC, Vigo). Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain.

GUERRA, 1992). Although cephalopods is a resource that is being exploited over the continental shelves (RATHJEN AND VOSS, 1987), actually, their catches represent about 2.9 million tonnes by year, which constitutes more than 2.5% of the total catches of marine organisms (FAO, 1996). Thus, taking into account studies on diet of their most important predators, CLARKE (1983) estimated that the oceanic cephalopod biomass exceed 300 million tonnes.

The first goal of researchers in Marine Biology is focused in analysing how the inner characteristics of a population of cephalopods and its environment determine and affect their productivity as a resource. Within the environmental aspects, several pathogenic vectors of different etiology constitutes the main source of "bioagressors" in the fishery exploitation of a resource. DOBSON AND MAY (1987) and SINDERMANN AND MCLEAN (1987) catalogued the effects of a broad variety of micro and macroparasites in several fish species of commercial interest. They pointed out parasites (virus, bacteria and parasitic protozoans) as the most virulent pathogenic vectors, increasing the mortality and reducing the reproductive potential of the host, whilst the pathogenic ability of macroparasites is expressed in a considerable reduction in the host condition (reducing the productivity and the commercial value).

The analysis and measurement of condition (inferred from the length-weight relationships) of the species of commercial interest is actually considered a common task in studies on Fishery Biology (BOLGER AND CONNOLLY, 1989). Studying the condition of any specimen implies that the organisms of higher weights, for a given size, are in better condition. Therefore, it is believed that the condition is a good indicator of the population "robustness, fitness or fatness", whilst growth can be defined as a combination of increments in body weight, condition and energetic concentration in tissues, representing the last expression of fitness (ADAMS AND MCLEAN, 1985; BOOTH AND KEAST, 1986).

Focusing these studies in the Galician coast, ommastrephids constitute an important resource which is reflected by an average catch of about 1,000 tonnes per year during the last fifteen years (GONZÁLEZ, RASERO AND GUERRA, 1996). Despite the studies undertaken about the two main ommastrephid species collected in the Galician coast (*Illex coindetii* and *Todaropsis eblanae*), it is necessary to improve the knowledge about some biological and ecological aspects that could affect the productivity of the ommastrephid stock, the parasitism being one of the most important (PASCUAL ET AL., 1996).

The existence of causal relationships expressed in modifications of ecological potential (assuming the term condition as an indirect measurement of productivity) of the ommastrephid *Illex coindetii* and *Todaropsis eblanae* stocks in Galician waters and the high infestation of several post-embryonic stages of a copepod crustacean of the genus *Pennella* observed in the gills is studied in the present paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fishery statistics in landings and economic value from 1980 to 1991 were obtained from GONZÁLEZ ET AL. (1996). Monthly parasitological samplings (600 specimens per host species, *Illex coindetii* and *Todaropsis eblanae*) for ommastrephids were undertaken from November 1991 to November 1992 at the ports of Burela and Riveira (NW Spain), from the trawl fleet landing at these ports. Mantle length (ML) and body weight (BW) of the animals were annotated (PASCUAL, 1996). All the parasite larval stages of *Pennella* sp. were counted in each gill lamella for all the hosts following the methodology given by PASCUAL (1996).

The Condition Index K1 ($BW/ML^3 \times 100$) was calculated as an expression of "robustness" of the host individuals by reference to BOLGER AND CONNOLLY (1989). The normality of the distribution of the number of parasites in the host

populations was studied using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S Z= 1.6126; $p < 0.05$ for *I. coindetii*; K-S Z= 1.4614; $p < 0.05$ for *T. eblanae*). Due to the high aggregation observed in the distribution of parasites, generalised linear models were used (GLMs) to determine the influence of the gill parasite *Pennella* sp. on the condition of the ommastrephids (WILSON AND GRENFELL, 1997). The linear models were performed by reference to Weldon and Slauson (1986) when two important aspects of the regression had to be analysed: a) the strength of the relationship (variation in percentage of the dependent variable with a variation in an unit of the independent variable, estimated from the value of the slope), and b) the relative importance of the relationship (the proportion of the variation associated with the relationship, estimated from the value of the determination coefficient R^2). Statistical analyses were undertaken using the software SPSS/WIN 6. 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interannual values of prevalence of infestation by *Pennella* sp. in the ommastrephid stocks ranged from 90% to 100% in *Illex coindetii* and *Todaropsis eblanae*, respectively. Fitting to the regression models clearly indicates that parasitism implies some 2.2% (Pearson correlation coefficient: $r = -0.1990$; $p < 0.01$) and

8.1% ($r = -0.296$; $p < 0.001$) of the variation in condition of the ommastrephids, reducing the condition of *I. coindetii* and *T. eblanae* over 8.8 and 21.1% respectively (PASCUAL, GESTAL AND ABOLLO, 1997). Taking into account that landings during the period 1980-1991 were about 13,000 tonnes (GONZÁLEZ ET AL., 1996), and that 50% of the landings belong to each of the mentioned ommastrephid species, it can be inferred that the reduction in biomass of infested squid were 143 and 527 tonnes for *I. coindetii* and *T. eblanae*, respectively. Assuming an average value of 125 ptas/kg of squid, it can be inferred that the infestation by *Pennella* sp. meant losses of about 83.6 millions of ptas. for the period 1980-1991. The annual economic loss for the fishery sector due to the infested stock is thus estimated in some 7.6 millions ptas.

This overview highlights that parasitism is not only an important zoonotic problem but an important economic problem at the time of management of infested stocks, as previously reported by several authors in some other fisheries (MALOUF, 1986).

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